

FORM 3

THE PATENTS ACT,
1970 (39 of 1970)

and

THE PATENTS RULES,
2003

**STATEMENT AND UNDERTAKING UNDER
SECTION 8**

(See section 8; Rule 12)

1. Name of the applicant(s).	We Badhe Pravin Dattatraya and Badhe Ashwini Pravin hereby declare:
2. Name, address and nationality of the joint applicant.	(i) that We have not made any application for the same/substantially the same invention outside India

3. To be signed by the applicant or his authorized registered patent agent.	Signature.
4. Name of the natural person who has signed.	(Mr Badhe Pravin Dattatraya).
	To The Controller of Patents, The Patent Office, at Mumbai
Note.- Strike out whichever is not applicable;	